

Websites as support tools for learning the English language

Sitios Web como herramientas de apoyo para el aprendizaje del idioma Inglés

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Abstract—The Websites contribute much to the learning of the English language, facilitating the teaching of the teachers through the use of dynamic strategies they help to reinforce the cognitive approach with greater ease, since it allows to develop the language skills with precision, improving the communication of the students in the classroom, which separates the ambiguous strategies used with the traditional method of learning. These technological tools are important in the variety of interactive activities and practices for understanding the English language, improving the motivation of students in the improvement of the activities of the subject. According to the results of this research, it was possible to show the change in behavior and assimilation, in such a way that 78 % of the students who received the subject of English with the contribution of the Websites, which allowed them to learn more satisfactory since they had interactive activities for their benefit. The quantitative and qualitative methods of observation were applied, taking as sample 144 students from modules 1, 2, 3 and 4 of English, using a survey of 10 questions oriented to the use of Websites as a support tool for the learning the English language, which is a contribution of great importance for both students and teachers in the inter-learning of this foreign language.

Keywords—English, knowledge, sustenance implements, Websites

Resumen—Los sitios Web contribuyen significativamente en el aprendizaje del idioma Inglés, facilitando la enseñanza de los maestros ya que a través del uso de estrategias dinámicas ayudan a reforzar el enfoque cognitivo con mayor facilidad, ya que permite desarrollar las destrezas del idioma con precisión, mejorando la interrelación de los alumnos en el aula de clase, lo cual aparta a las estrategias ambiguas utilizadas con el método tradicional de aprendizaje. Estas herramientas tecnológicas radican su importancia en la variedad de actividades interactivas y prácticas para la comprensión del idioma Inglés, favoreciendo la motivación de los estudiantes en el desarrollo de las actividades propias de la asignatura. De acuerdo con los resultados de esta investigación se logró evidenciar el cambio de comportamiento y de asimilación, de tal manera, que el 78 % de los alumnos que recibieron la asignatura de Inglés con el aporte de los sitios Web, lo cual les permitió un aprendizaje más satisfactorio ya que contaron con actividades interactivas para su beneficio. Se utilizaron los métodos de la observación, cuantitativo y cualitativo, teniendo como muestra a 144 educandos de los módulos 1, 2, 3 y 4 de Inglés, empleándose una encuesta de 10 preguntas orientadas en el uso de sitios Web como herramienta de apoyo para el aprendizaje del idioma Inglés, lo cual es un aporte de gran importancia tanto para estudiantes como para docentes en el interaprendizaje de este idioma extranjero.

Palabras Claves—aprendizaje, instrumentos tecnológicos, Inglés, espacios Web

INTRODUCTION

The irruption of the Internet represents one of the most magnificence innovations in these times since it has led to innumerable changes in student, personal, professional, social and family life.

Currently, the English language represents a very complex subject for students who study the different modules of English which leads to disinterest, withdrawal of the subject and poor performance of learning, disfavor the exit profile of graduates, which is why it is very important to add Websites oriented to the teaching of this foreign language, which allow the acquisition skills and abilities developed in this subject. Regardless of the support material available in the English texts used in the modules, add websites as a substitute measure in the orientation and practice of English language skills is

important. This work was made with a sample of 144 students of the modules of English 1, 2, 3 and 4 of the State University of Milagro, obtaining as a result of the study, the need to merge websites as teaching strategies to motivate students in their autonomous learning that allows them to do various activities such as grammar and vocabulary, pronunciation, readings, audio practices, questionnaires, worksheets, crosswords, up-to-date news, among others. Also, in these sites, you can find dictionaries with or without images, which helps when researching.

In the learning of the English language, the incorporation of the internet in technological advances allows to enhance the acquisition of knowledge, improving the skills of the English language, since at present there are innumerable sites, pages or web portals where learners can find a variety of exercises and explanations that allow them to reinforce their learning. The importance of using the Internet, through the websites, activates a phase of independence and autonomy, through which students discover for themselves the pedagogical subjects and

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resources of the English language according to their interests and needs.

Online educational resources found on the Internet include printed, visual and audio materials stored in electronic formats and other teaching-learning processes, which are free to be used or downloaded by students at any time. That is to say, students will be able to use tools and resources that the Internet provides and that will help to relate to what has been learned and the present life.

In this globalized world, the learning of the English language has become an inescapable priority and the Internet presents diverse activities that are highly productive and recreational to reinforce the skills of this language. (1)(Díaz and Bruce, 2011)

The learning of a foreign language involves several factors that converge and interrelate so that the student achieves the mastery of a language. The process of learning English is renewed with the use of the Internet, whether inside or outside the classroom, that is, accompanied by the teacher or autonomously. (2)(Totano, 2017)

Therefore, learning the English language is related to the development of communication skills, such as listening and observing, so the Internet provides an opportunity for students to improve their language.

Educational focus of the English language in Ecuador

The Ministry of Education of Ecuador is working to improve the national education system, incorporating several English programs to improve the level of knowledge of this language as a foreign language. At present, the Project for Strengthening the Teaching of English as a Foreign Language is presented, which assumes as its main objective that Ecuadorian schoolchildren obtain a functional level of use of the English language. However, these programs are focused on English teachers with the initiative to strengthen the knowledge and methodologies of English teachers to ensure the level of linguistic competence of the students. (3)(Hernández, 2014)

These goals base on concrete initiatives focused on the updating of the national curricula of that subject, elaboration and delivery of books established to these curricula, as well as the professional development of teachers of active English and the continuous improvement of professional training in the English as a foreign language, necessary to aim at development and competitiveness with the globalized world. (4)(Navas; Real; Mayorga and Pacheco, 2016)

That is, not only requires the continuous preparation of the English teacher to the foreign language, but the way forward is to guide and make sure the proper use of the Internet by students, which will help the development of language skills and the constant practice of the study programs of this foreign language. (Paucar, 2010)

Due to the variety of changes in this globalized world, technological advances are a tool that provides support in different fields. In the education system, it is much more demanding because it plays a preponderant role in the teaching of the different subjects and with greater precision in the subject

of English. Therefore, teachers should carry out alternatives to associate the use of the Internet in their activities using this technological tool when teaching their class. (5)(González, 2012)

It is important to mention that not all teachers use these resources, ensuring that students feel unmotivated to act in class, since; many students are kinaesthetic since they learn by observing and listening, in such a way that with the projections they acquire a better accuracy of language skills. (6)(Richard, Jack, and Renandya, Willy, 2008)

This research work is born to reference the importance that technological interactive resources should have within the English language teaching, having a class planning, it must include the Internet as the primary tool to work with the different resources Interactive that allow maintaining the students' attention and with this the knowledge acquisition and developing the skills of the English language could be generated, fortifying the standards of the general, holistic and by processes, increasing the students' motivation to accept the subject and opening the opportunity for them to build much. (7)(Maridueña, 2014)

At present, 70 % of the information found on the Internet is in English and more than 80 % of all communications were written in English, which allows us to find this tool as the main means of education in all its areas.

Project to Strengthen the Teaching of English as a Foreign Language

The project to strengthen the teaching of English as a foreign language arises from the need to improve the inter-learning of this language, due to poor educational performance and the result of the process obtained.

The Ministry of Education established, as a rule, the need for teachers to have a continuous improvement and, at the same time, that students get all the competences of the English language considering the exit profile of the students.

In addition, in accordance with the provisions of the Ministry of Education, teachers to access the program "It is time to teach in Ecuador", must have an international certification of English language skill level B2 according to what indicates in the Common European Framework for Languages (MCER). (8)(Educación, Proyecto It is time to teach in Ecuador)

In addition, this project has of benefiting teachers on developing on playful learning materials, which delivered in each school period to the different educational establishments, multimedia material such as audio and videos as a support tool on English teaching language.

Due to changes in the global economy, the English language makes up a linguistic communications platform worldwide, becoming an opportunity for the educational, personal, social, and work advancement.

English language learning

The subject of teaching English as a foreign language remains controversial and controversial. Everywhere there are

defenders and detractors of the different approaches in the learning theories that we have known until today, mainly those rules and techniques to combine the various components of language and language skills.

However, today we still ask ourselves why our students graduate from our universities after five years of consecutive study of the English language, without communicating correctly requiring the communicative method to highlight to make the goals of the program. We believe it is important to take into account the conditions in which this teaching develops in our country and the characteristics of our students if we want to have a graduate by the current medical requirements of the English-speaking countries, which is also the demand of our Ministry of Public Health. (9)(Roten, Miguel Angel Quinio, 2016)

The English language is of great importance worldwide, due to the need it represents among people in general in different fields of action, so it demands the need to learn it and for this it requires the use of the Internet tool which provides various interactive activities as support to support their autonomous, group or general learning, incorporating new teaching methods for languages.

Collaborative spaces and learning the English language

Focused on universal history, the teaching-learning of languages has progressed through the currents of thought, leaving aside the grammatical teaching. In the learning of the English language the incorporation of collaborative tools that allow the understanding of the language and, at the same time, the interaction between the students to overcome barriers of understanding immersed in the learning process of this language. (10)(Ramírez, 2013)

Currently, the Internet, technological resources, virtual and social networks offer the opportunity to millions of people around the world to meaningful and authentic linguistic use that definitely help in the activities that take place in the classroom.

These learning opportunities are more likely to being interactive, social and practical so that students can carry out their activities using this tool. In addition, they can use to download several activities placed by teachers who have designed these virtual classrooms, which allows them to easily develop activities suggested by teachers, such as links, virtual interactive programs, resources in pdf, which contain aspects of the language learning. (11)(Salas, 2016)

Importance of the virtual classroom as a tool for learning English

The Virtual Classroom makes up a variable platform that provides tools that help virtual teaching and creating of collaborative spaces for working groups. This tool based on the e-learning platform called Moodle. (12)(Fernández Pampillón, 2008)

This process is due to the fact that education, in general, has been implemented to the use of technologies as a support in the

learning of students of all levels, moreover, to languages today there are innumerable activities in different virtual platforms where The student can get new insights and opportunities in the multiple fields of social relationships that benefit their daily practice. (Jansson, 2011)

The implementation of the e-learning model as a strategy makes up the way for a change with the traditional teaching of generating knowledge in the classrooms, since it shows much more dynamic activities and thus satisfies the communication and interaction need of the students and In addition, the strengthening of autonomous work that helps in the learning process. (13)(Dorado, 2012)

Training in the use of the e-learning platform is necessary, therefore, teachers who use this resource must adapt to this system to create virtual spaces as part of the educational process. (14)(Gutiérrez, Herrera and Pérez, 2017)

Websites for learning English

Nowadays you can find a variety of websites that help in the learning of languages at all levels, that is, they are a continuous and free reach support for all people worldwide. Its diversity of scope facilitates the use of exercises by teachers, keeping this tool in the different activities that take place inside and outside the classroom. (15)(Peñuela, 2012)

As reinforcement to learning in the classroom, students can search for topics or activities of the English language. As an example, the following is mentioned:

Easy World of English

It is a website that is designed so that people can develop learning English language activities at their own pace, repeat a lesson as many times as necessary and learn vocabulary without the need for translation. The learning system includes components of grammar, pronunciation, reading and an illustrated and interactive dictionary. (16)(Saza, 2016)

The latest technology used on this page provides the opportunity to develop activities prior to the revision of rules and easy exercises for learning the English language. (17)(Sheehan, 2013)

All things grammar

It is a website that serves as a guidebook with audio, dialogue, reading and writing activities. On this platform, there are grammar and vocabulary activities and an infinity of additional resources to complete spaces, crossword puzzles, etc.

BBC Learning English

BBC Learning English has taught English worldwide since 1943, delivering free audio, video and text materials to students around the world. In addition, this site provides multimedia materials to integrate the needs of students.

The components that contain each course are independent, which provides the student the opportunity to do their practice on their own. This means that the student can choose the best way to study for them; following a complete course or after the individual materials most of them. (18)(Oliveira, 2013)

Language Guide

Illustrated dictionary with a variety of topics, including organs of the human body and fauna in different environments

Oxford University Press

It is a global e-learning solution for learning English developed to practice different activities for beginner to advanced students that include grammar, pronunciation, hearing, and spelling. (Press)

Humans of New York

This page is designed to tell daily, happy, sad or inspiring stories in the simple language of real people living in New York. Currently, HONY has more than 20 million followers worldwide.

Easy English

EasyEnglish is a collection of online questions and tests in English designed for ESL students. The tests come in three levels (easy, medium and difficult). Scores and answers are provided and help participants improve English language skills.

How do you do

Connection with native speakers of the United States or the United Kingdom, to practice writing and speaking skills in English, conversing with native speakers or with other English learners.

Voice of America News

Watch short TV shows or listen to a radio that tells stories on three levels. This website is specifically focused on the news around the world.

Test Your English

This website is from Cambridge University Press and is available for checking the level of English, after which it offers pre-test preparation courses for knowledge of the language. (19)(Assessment, 2015)

Learn English

LearnEnglish is owned by the British Council and is designed for the learning of the English language autonomously, for which high-quality resources and level tests are demonstrated in order to tone the online course. This site teaches English for business and presents mobile activities, games, and videos, among others.

It should be noted that they have several benefits such as grammar activities, vocabulary, reading, writing, audio, quizzes, lessons, tests, pronunciation and even tips on British culture, valuable to improve English language learning. (20)(Página Web: Una herramienta virtual para la enseñanza - aprendizaje)

Duolingo

It is a language e-learning platform. It is based on an informal and everyday language, with a friendly deal with clear orientation, with an assessment of digital linguistic competence.

English page

Study verb tenses, prepositions, vocabulary and grammar through forums, weekly lessons or specific tasks.

Moodle e-learning platform

It is one of the most popular free software. It arises as a result of the collaborative effort of a team of developers who wrote this open source software. Moodle is an extremely flexible platform in which, thanks to extensions, modules, and themes, you can create an environment that suits you. You can install Moodle on your server or host services. One aspect that has improved in the latest versions has been the connection and graphic adaptation possibilities. It is a platform that I recommend for its flexibility, ease of use and constant improvements. (21)(Nedeva and Dimova, 2010)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methods of observation, quantitative and qualitative, were used, which contributed to this research work, using a survey with 10 questions focused on this process, it was considered a sample of 144 students, that is, 5 %, which was taken from a universe of 2,880 students of the different modules of English at the State University of Milagro. Taking into consideration a survey format that confirmed the verification of the results and allowed the conclusion of this investigation. The following formula was applied:

$$n = \frac{(N \times p \times q)}{(N - 1) \times E^2 + p \times q} \times Z^2$$

$$n = \frac{(2880 \times 0,5 \times 0,5)}{(2880 - 1) \times 0,003 + 0,5 \times 0,5} \times 5$$

$$n = \frac{720}{820 \times 0,003 + 0,5 \times 0,5} \times 5$$

$$n = \frac{720}{5}$$

$$n = 144$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For this research work, the survey was carried out to 144 students, 64 male and 80 female of the different English modules of the Second Semester 2016. Likewise, the average age of the respondents was taken into account, the same one that showed a higher incidence in students ranging from 18 to 25 years of age.

Table 1 Students ranging

OPTIONS	QUANTITY	PERCENTAGE
Module 1	19	13%
Module 2	33	23%
Module 3	52	36%
Module 4	40	28%
Total	144	100%

Source: Students survey

After obtaining the results of the surveys made to the students, we try to specify the results based on the questions of the survey.

Table 2 Use of Websites or virtual classroom

OPTIONS	QUANTITY	PERCENTAGE
Yes	67	47%
No	77	53%
Total	144	100%

Source: Students survey

Graphic 1 Use of Websites or virtual classroom

In question 1, 53% of the students indicated that they have not used Websites intended for learning the English language, which shows the disinterest of the respondents in using these pedagogical resources as reinforcement to improve the knowledge of this foreign language.

Table 3 Frequency in using Websites or virtual classrooms

OPTIONS	QUANTITY	PERCENTAGE
High	43	30%
Medium	40	28%
Low	61	42%
Total	144	100%

Source: Students survey

Graphic 2 Frequency in using Websites

In the second question, 42% of the respondents stated that they constantly use English language learning websites, to strengthening this subject.

Table 4 Know the benefits of several Web pages

OPTIONS	QUANTITY	PERCENTAGE
Yes	108	75%
No	36	25%
Total	144	100%

Source: Students survey

Graphic 3 Know the benefits of several Web pages

In question 3, 78% of the students were optimistic and open to know the benefits that some Web pages have for learning the English language since they have interactive motivating activities for that purpose.

Table 5 Register on a website

OPTIONS	QUANTITY	PERCENTAGE
Yes	121	84%
No	23	16%
Total	144	100%

Source: Students survey

Graphic 4 Register on a website

In question 4 about the interest of registering on a website for learning the English language, 84 % of the respondents expressed their pleasure to improve their level of knowledge of this language.

Table 6 Importance of the English language

OPTIONS	QUANTITY	PERCENTAGE
Yes	128	89%
No	16	11%
Total	144	100%

Source: Students survey

Graphic 5 Importance of the English language

Question 5, which is related to the importance of learning the English language, 89 % of the students recognized that indeed the learning of this foreign language plays a relevant role in the personal and professional field.

Table 7 English language skills

OPTIONS	QUANTITY	PERCENTAGE
Use of English	47	21%
Reading	32	14%
Writing	41	19%
Listening	28	13%
Speaking	21	10%
All of them	51	23%
Total	220	100%

Source: Students survey

Graphic 6 English language skills

Regarding question 6 related to improving English language skills, the respondents selected the ones they wanted to improve, which demonstrates their interest in learning the English language.

Table 8 Importance of English Web pages

OPTIONS	QUANTITY	PERCENTAGE
High	73	51%
Medium	53	37%
Low	18	12%
Total	144	100%

Source: Students survey

Graphic 7 Importance of English Web pages

In question 7 about the level of importance of English Web pages, 51 % of students highlighted the quality of these sites useful for learning the English language.

Table 9 Essential technological tools

OPTIONS	QUANTITY	PERCENTAGE
Websites	63	49%
Virtual platforms	49	34%
Interactive Software	17	12%
Others	15	10%
Total	144	105%

Source: Students survey

Graphic 8 Essential technological tools

In question 8 related to the technological tools beneficial for learning the English language, the respondents took into consideration the different Websites, which show that they clearly show that these tools help to reinforce their knowledge.

Table 10 Interactive programs

OPTIONS	QUANTITY	PERCENTAGE
Yes	128	89%
No	16	11%
Total	144	100%

Source: Students survey

Graphic 9 Interactive programs

In question 9, 89 % of the students mentioned their approval about the opportunities offered by the interactive programs and virtual classrooms to improve the learning of the English language.

Table 11 Know some English websites

OPTIONS	QUANTITY	PERCENTAGE
Easy World of English	38	26%
BBC Learning English	34	24%
Duolingo	57	40%
Others	15	10%
Total	144	100%

Source: Students survey

Graphic 10 Know some English websites

In question 10, the students indicated knowing several of the websites and/or virtual classrooms that were presented, which indicates that they understand the need to merge these tools to develop their skills in learning the English language.

DISCUSSION

The complexity to learn English tends on requiring the need to resort to websites as technological tools to improve the skills of this foreign language, considering 89 % of the respondents in question 4, which corroborates with the attribute by Nayeli Gutiérrez, Santa Herrera and Yazmin Pérez, in the article ICT in the teaching of English in basic education.

According to question 9, 89 % of respondents argue that websites and virtual classrooms are interactive platforms that provide interaction with other students, motivating them to practice and learn the English language.

These collaborative tools are undoubtedly websites that strengthen the developing of English language skills. These sites find on the Internet and are mostly free, that is, free to practice the English language autonomously according to the needs of those who need these resources, so it is essential that teachers use these benefits as teaching strategies that reinforce and motivate this process, which correlates with the criteria of María Ramírez Montoya, in her text Teaching strategies and strategies for creative environments, since it highlights to join these technological resources for the inter-learning of the English language.

It is important to highlight that meaningful learning adopts a change of the traditional structure forming successful people, with classes of coprinllaborative environment that highlights the ideas of the teacher, who maintains constant control of the strategic activities applied with the use of collaborative tools and improve the acquirer of knowledge.

CONCLUSIONS

This research project demonstrates the importance that now represent technological tools or resources as an aid to learning

the English language, because students acquire knowledge of the language in a much more dynamic and interesting way making the difference of traditional learning since the strategies used to contribute to a more open relationship between the student and the teacher, which represents a quality academic preparation, acquiring competitive axes in accordance with current demands.

On the other hand, it is very eloquent to find that the inclusion of English websites contributes to the development of cognitive and social skills of students, ensuring fairness of opportunities for those involved allowing an inclusive sense in the educational process.

The English websites serve as accompaniment in the inter-learning of this language, which allows reinforcing the different language skills and thus improve the learning results, which is measured in the students' grades; that is to say, with the help of the benefits of the English websites, the percentage of students dropping out of the courses taken in this research work has been reduced, due to the interest they have shown in the use of interactive activities through virtual classrooms or websites.

This generates a positive reaction for the benefit of the students who study the different modules of English at the State University of Milagro.

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REFERENCIAS

- [1] C. H. D. Larenas and L. J. Bruce, "El aprendizaje del inglés y el uso de tecnologías: percepciones de estudiantes y profesores de inglés del nivel secundario chileno," *Matices en Lenguas Extranjeras*, no. 5, pp. 1-37, 2011.
- [2] M. N. T. Becerra, "El docente y el uso de herramientas tecnológicas de enseñanza-aprendizaje en la educación básica ecuatoriana," *Journal of Science and Research: Revista Ciencia e Investigación*, vol. 2, no. 7, pp. 10-14, 2017.
- [3] E. Hernández Chérrez, *El B-learning como estrategia metodológica para mejorar el proceso de enseñanza-aprendizaje de los estudiantes de inglés de la modalidad semipresencial del departamento especializado de idiomas de la Universidad Técnica de Ambato*. PhD thesis, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, 2014.
- [4] Y. N. Montes, I. R. Poveda, S. P. Mendoza, and A. L. M. Albán, "Los procesos de enseñanza y aprendizaje del

- idioma inglés a través de los entornos virtuales de aprendizaje/the processes of teaching and learning english through a virtual learning environment,” *Ciencia Unemi*, vol. 8, no. 13, pp. 47–55, 2015.
- [5] J. González *et al.*, “Uso de las nuevas tecnologías en la enseñanza de lenguas extranjeras,” 2012.
- [6] J. C. Richards and W. A. Renandya, *Methodology in language teaching: An anthology of current practice*. Cambridge university press, 2002.
- [7] J. Maridueña Macancela, “Recursos interactivos tecnológicos y su repercusión en el inter aprendizaje del idioma inglés,” *Revista RES NON VERBA*, vol. 5, pp. 193–210, 2014.
- [8] R. M. Torres del Castillo, “Nuevo papel docente.¿ qué modelo de formación y para qué modelo educativo?,” *Perfiles educativos*, no. 82, 1998.
- [9] M. A. Q. Roten, “The impact of using guided writing techniques on chilean adults’ efl writing production,” *Modern Journal of Language Teaching Methods*, vol. 6, no. 1, p. 642, 2016.
- [10] M. S. R. Montoya, *Modelos y estrategias de enseñanzas para ambientes innovadores*. Editorial Digital del Tecnológico de Monterrey, 2018.
- [11] J. Salas-Alvarado, “El aprendizaje colaborativo en la clase de inglés: El caso del curso de comunicación oral i de la sede del pacífico de la universidad de costa rica,” *Revista Educación*, pp. 1–19, 2016.
- [12] A. E. Zabala Parreño, “Diseño de un sistema de capacitación continua de buenas prácticas de laboratorio para microbiología aplicada sobre una plataforma e-learning,” Master’s thesis, PUCE, 2015.
- [13] C. D. Perea, “Estrategias de enseñanza-aprendizaje y modelos en entornos de e-learning,” *Multiárea: revista de didáctica*, no. 3, pp. 103–126, 2008.
- [14] N. Barroz and D. Carolina, “La pizarra digital interactiva y el proceso de escritura del idioma inglés en los estudiantes de décimo año de educación general básica de la unidad educativa tomas martínez, parroquia san fernando del cantón ambato, provincia de tungurahua,” B.S. thesis, Universidad Técnica de Ambato. Facultad de Ciencias humanas y de la ... , 2016.
- [15] P. Pardo and Y. Bonet, “La página web como herramienta didáctica en el aprendizaje de vocabulario en inglés,” 2016.
- [16] I. D. Saza-Garzón, “Estrategias didácticas en tecnologías web para ambientes virtuales de aprendizaje,” *Praxis*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 103–110, 2016.
- [17] S. Sheehan, *British Council ELT Research Papers*, vol. 1. British Council, 2013.
- [18] R. M. O. Carneiro, “English phonetics and phonology: the contributions of the website bbc learning english to the teaching of pronunciation,” *Entrepalavras*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 292–305, 2013.
- [19] I. M. Macancela and I. R. Poveda, “Módulo cero y su impacto positivo en el aprendizaje del idioma inglés como lengua extranjera en los alumnos del primer semestre de la universidad estatal de milagro,” *Revista Científica y Tecnológica UPSE*, vol. 4, no. 2, 2017.
- [20] D. M. G. Ibarra, “Página web: Una herramienta virtual para la enseñanza-aprendizaje de la genética en el grado octavo de la institución educativa maría cristina arango de la ciudad de neiva, huila,” *Bio-grafía Escritos sobre la biología y su enseñanza*, pp. 1220–1228, 2015.
- [21] V. Nedeva and E. Dimova, “Some advantages of e-learning in english language training,” *Trakia Journal of Sciences*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 21–28, 2010.